

VIETNAM FROM COP26 – FROM COMMITMENT TO ACTIONS, CUTTING-EDGE SOLUTIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY TRANSITION AND TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION AT VIETNAM ELECTRICITY (EVN)

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, in the context that fossil energy sources are increasingly depleted, along with the issues of climate change becoming increasingly urgent, the energy transition, especially the energy transition in the electricity industry, has been getting more and more attention. In 2021, at the 26th United Nations Climate Change Conference, as known as COP26 for short, Vietnam, one of the countries most affected by climate change, participated in the Global Declaration on the transition from coal to green power and considers this point as an important orientation toward a low-carbon economy and green growth in the coming decades. Accordingly, the Draft Power Master Plan VIII has been issued with the goal of reducing dependence on coal-fired power plants, giving high priority to renewable energy development with reasonable structure and distribution and having over 75% renewable energy in the whole country by 2045. The targets of the electricity source development to 2025, 2030 and 2045 are presented in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Vietnam's targets to 2045 of the electricity source development (Source: Developed in the research)

Even before committing at COP26, Vietnam Government has issued many incentive policies to develop renewable energy in power industry. By the end of 2021, the total installed capacity of wind and solar power sources reached 20,670 MW, accounting for nearly 27% of the total installed capacity of the whole system. The electricity output from this power source has reached 31.5 billion kWh, accounting for 12.27% of total electricity production of the whole system. From 2016 to 2021, energy from oil, natural gas and hydro-electric are decreasing over the years. Meanwhile, renewable energy represents a rapid growth, from 0.32% in 2018 to 6% in 2021. Although the results in energy transition of power industry in Vietnam are demonstrating the positive signals and effectiveness from government's policy, there are many challenges, which Vietnam must face to achieve the goal as Power Master Plan VIII. The Ministry of Industry and Trade has studied and developed many scenarios and plans to published the Power Master Plan VIII in the direction of reducing dependence on coal-fired power plants and giving high priority to renewable energy development with reasonable structure and distribution. At that time, Vietnam Electricity, as known as EVN, the pioneer in Vietnam's power industry, must shoulder a huge responsibility and need to face challenges in energy transition such as investment capital, technology transformation, developing infrastructure of electricity system in whole country, etc... Besides, there are many environmental factors affecting the transition of energy industry such as policies, economic growth, income level, etc and the those are the factors which EVN cannot control or take action to change in the short term. However, by examining which are the factors, how those factors impact on the energy transition in Vietnam, EVN can focus and determine action plans in accordance with fluctuations of political-economic environment.

PURPOSE OF THIS STUDY

Based on the context as well as the urgency of developing research with a scientific basis, this study is deployed. The process of conducting research is the pro-

cess by which the author finds the answers to four questions: (1) What the transition will look like and its time frame. (2) What are the factors (currently) in favor of EVN transition and what factors are against EVN transition. (3) What types of technical capability and knowledge EVN would need to achieve this transition? (4) What should EVN do to take advantage of factors with positive influences, or minimize and avoid the effects from factors with negative impacts while implementing the schedule of energy transition? This study also reviews the previous research and experiences of other countries in the energy transitions field and provides a preference for the research in the future.

GAP IN THE LITERATURE

Energy transitions are not a new matter. In the 19th century, it was the transition from using wood to using coal; and in the 20th century was from coal to oil. Energy transition includes everything related to all energy sources, from the issues of transport and use energy in industry, in buildings and within homes, to powering thermal applications such as heating, air conditioning, cooking, etc. Not only that, but it also relates to the operation of all equipment. The energy transitions in this 21st century is very urgent and different from the past since its relationship with protecting the planet from the greatest threat it has ever had to face, and of doing so as quickly as possible. IEA (2019) report that “there are not any other alternative scenarios of the energy transition for mankind to combat with the current and future global environmental pollution”. “Energy transition is the change in the composition (structure) of primary energy supply, the gradual shift from a specific pattern of energy provision to a new start of an energy system” (Smil, 2016). “Energy transition refers to the global energy sector’s shift from fossil-based systems of energy production and consumption – including oil, natural gas and coal – to renewable energy sources like wind and solar, as well as lithium-ion batteries” (SPGlobal, 2020). “The change has been primarily driven by government policy and consumer preference, but as the cost of renewable energy continues to fall, the global energy sector and the market will naturally shift towards renewables” (Koons, 2022). Energy transitions are complex undertaking that encompass techno-economics features as well as social aspects (Mejía-Montero, Alonso-Serna, & Altamirano-Allende, 2020). Moreover, further complexities emerge when energy transitions are initiated in pursuit of energy security (G. Valkenburg, 2016). Besides the environmental issues, energy transition includes both economic and social aspects towards a “sustainable” energy system in the sense of “sustainable development”, which has been mentioned in the 1987 Brundtland Report of the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development. Furthermore, “the scale and speed of development of renewable energy sources need to be suitable to the conditions of each country” (Nam, 2021). Regarding the energy transition issues, the International Renewable Energy Agency

(IRENA) (2021) reported that the energy transition has positive influences on economic growth, job creation and human welfare. Energy transformation will bring deep structural changes to societies and economies (ÖUNMAA, 2021). In the opposite side, it also “depends on different factors, policies, geographical location, and energy flows in the region” (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020). In longterm, economic growth, population growth and inflation rate show negative impact on energy transition while CO₂ emissions, geopolitical risk, exchange rate and financial openness are determined with positive influence on energy transition movement (Rasoulinezhad, Taghizadeh-Hesary, Sung, & Panthamit, 2020). Dogan and Oztuk (2017) also found a negative relationship between green energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in the United States during period from 1980 to 2014. In the countries in Asia, Economic growth has a positive relationship with energy transition, while CO₂ emissions negatively influence energy transition (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020). Caetano, Marques, Afonso, & Vieira (2022) shows that “Foreign Direct Investment may increase pollution by increasing overall energy consumption, rather than by transferring polluting industries; and energy transition could be achieved with out the polluting effect of Foreign Direct Investment” (Caetano, Marques, Afonso, & Vieira, 2022).

Studies that have been carried out in other countries around the world have proven a number of factors that affect energy transition such as economic growth, population growth rate, CO₂ emissions, geographical factors, politics, government, exchange rate, etc. The results from these studies help countries to have a better understand about their energy transition. However, the findings from the studies that have been done are sometimes not the same. *Some factors was demonstrated with positive impact in this research, but showed negative influences in others.* This depends on the conditions and context of that country. However, these studies still have scientific value and are used as a supplement to the scientific basis of energy conversion pathways. In Vietnam, there have not been many studies on this topic, especially research using quantitative methods, which lead to be lack of researches with objectivity and high reliability to establish the basis of energy transition. From there, it is necessary to conduct both qualitative interviews with energy expert and EVN leadership to gain deeper insights into the practical and a quantitative research in this field.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL /THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Regarding the energy transition issues, the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) (2021) reported that the energy transition has positive influences on economic growth, job creation and human welfare. Energy transformation will bring deep structural changes to societies and economies (ÖUNMAA, 2021). Socacool (2016) cited by Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad (2020) concluded that the speed of energy transition “is not similar among countries and depends on different factors, policies, geographical location, and energy flows in the region” (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020).

Dogan and Oztuk (2017) found a negative relationship between green energy consumption and CO2 emissions in the United States during period from 1980 to 2014. Ozcan and Ozturk (2019) focused on the relationship between renewable energy consumption and economic growth in different emerging economies for the period of 1990–2016. The major findings showed evidence of the existence of the neutrality hypothesis due to the non-presence of the relationship between economic growth and renewable energy consumption. Taghaizadeh-Hesary and Rasoulinezhad (2020) conducted the study to determine how energy transitions patterns depend on economic variables in Asian economics, classifying based on income level of countries. Two researchers revealed that economic growth has a positive relationship with energy transition, while CO2 emissions negatively influence energy transition. In a sectoral analysis of the role of Foreign Direct Investment in pollution and energy transition in OECD countries, Caetano, Marques, Afonso, & Vieira (2022) shows that “Foreign Direct Investment may increase pollution by increasing overall energy consumption, rather than by transferring polluting industries; and energy transition could be achieved with out the polluting effect of Foreign Direct Investment” (Caetano, Marques, Afonso, & Vieira, 2022). Sharvini et al (2018) stated that many countries in Asia such as Malaysia is highly dependent on fossil resources as oil, coal and natural gas. The electricity sector in Vietnam is the major consumer of fossil fuels, mainly coal.

Considering the analysis of Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad (2020) about energy transitions patterns in Asia, it assumes that there are two economics sectors consuming electricity generated by energy sources. It also can be understood that the demand for renewable and non-renewable energy comes from these two sectors only. These sectors are industrial sector and household/residential sector.

Industry’s energy transition demand is a function of the elasticities of production of labor and capital, the real output of industry sector, the price of energy, the exchange rate and the transportation cost of energy (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020).

The following equation represents the energy transition demand of industry sector:

$$ET_t^I = (1 - \alpha - \beta) \frac{P_t^Y Y_t^I}{e_t(P_t^E + T_t)}$$

Where:

ET^I is energy output of industrial production, which is considered as energy transition (share of renewables to non-renewables) in the industrial sectors.

α is the elasticity of production of capital

β is the elasticity of production of labor

$1-\alpha-\beta$ is the elasticity of production of energy resources is equal to.

P^Y is the price of the final production Y^I is the total output of industry.

e_t denotes the exchange rate

P^E denotes energy price.

Regarding the household energy demand, households maximize their utility with respect to their budget. Household energy transition demand is a function of the exchange rate, electricity tariff, transportation costs of energy, and the income level of the household, Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad (2020) develop the Lagrange function, then process to identify the household energy demand as below:

$$E_t^H = f(e_t, P_t^E, T_t, Y_t^H)$$

From the fomulas determining industry and household energy demand, the total energy transition demand is equal to the combined of two kind of demand. Therefore, the total energy demand (ET_t) is a function of different factors. The total energy transition demand as following equation:

$$ET_t = f(e_t, P_t^E, T_t, Y_t)$$

In details, P^E is the electricity tariff, and T denotes the transportation costs of energy, e is the exchange rate, and Y_t is the total GDP of the energy importer, which depends on the income level of households (YH_t) and the total output of the industry (YI_t) (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020).

Furthermore, in the operation from production to consumption of electricity system, the process of electricity production and consumption is required to take place at the same time and with same technical. This process always must be in balance situation (Binh, 2022). Electricity is produced where there is demand for it, because it is a non-storage commodity, due to the limited ability to store electricity in energy storage systems. From there, the total electricity demand will be considered as the total electricity consumption. By the way, as mentioned above, this research assumes that the total energy transition is the total demand of two main sectors in the economy, so the total energy transition is considered as total energy consumption. In other words, energy consumption will be used as representative variable for energy transition. It also takes advantage of public databases.

The proposal model is as Figure 1 below:

Figure1. The proposed research models (Source: The proposal of researcher)

Economic growth is an increase in the production of economic goods and services in one period compared with a previous period. It can be measured in nominal or real (adjusted to remove inflation) terms. Traditionally, aggregate economic growth is measured in terms of gross national product (GNP) or gross domestic product (GDP), although alternative metrics are sometimes used. In this study, economic growth is identified as GDP index. Some research comes up with the conclusion of negative relationship between economic growth and energy transition (Rasoulinezhad, Taghizadeh-Hesary, Sung, & Panthamit, 2020); Some of others shows the opposite results (IRENA, 2021; Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020). In this study, hhypothesis for investigation is as below:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between economic growth and energy transition.

H₁: There is a positive relationship between economic growth and energy transition.

Next, population growth is the rate at which the population is increased or decreased during a period (usually in a year) due to natural increase and net migration population, expressed as a percentage and the average population (or mid-year population). This variable was chosen as a proxy for price due to the shortage of data in some years. When population increases, demand also increases. According to the principle of supply and demand, if demand increases and supply remains constant, scarcity occurs, and the price will become higher. Since electricity in Vietnam is essential to modern life and tends to be less price sensitive (Binh, 2022), this relationship need to be investigated. Hypothesis H₂ is as below:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between population growth and energy transition,

H₂” There is a negative relationship between population growth and energy transition.

Exchange rate was determined as a factor affecting energy consumption as well as energy transition. “Currency devaluation has an expansionary effect which enhances economic growth at the cost of high energy consumption” (Shah, et al., 2022). Exchange rate depreciation increases energy consumption in both the short and long runs (Shah, et al., 2022). A similar result also was demonstrated on the research of Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad (2020). Hypothesis H₃ is as below:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and energy transition

H₃: There is a negative relationship between exchange rate and energy transition

CO₂ emission is indicated as a factor with negative relationship with energy transition in most of previous researches (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad, 2020; Shah, et al., 2022). Hypothesis H₄ is as below

H₀: There is no significant relationship between CO₂ emission and energy transition.

H₄: There is a negative relationship between CO₂ emission and energy transition.

METHODOLOGY

Applying the model of Taghizadeh-Hesary & Rasoulinezhad (2020), in this study, energy transition (Renewable energy consumption/ non-renewable energy consumption) is considered as a dependent variable. Meanwhile, official exchange rate, economics growth, population growth and CO₂ emissions will be the independent variables. The equation of energy transition is as below:

$$ET_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EG + \beta_2 ER + \beta_3 CE + \beta_4 PG$$

In which:

ET_t is energy transition in year t and is determined by the ration of Renewable energy consumption in year t and non-renewable energy consumption in year t.

β₀ represents the fixed effects.

EG: Economic growth in year t-1

ER: Exchange rate in year t-1

CE: CO₂ Emissions in year t-1

PG: Population growth in year t-1

Using the data of independent variables with a 1-year lag is to avoid endogeneity problems since the energy transition might influence other variables. For example, the higher energy transition might affect economic growth positively and reduce CO₂ emissions.

In this study, the model is estimated by Stata software with three different regression methods, namely Pooled OLS, fixed effects model (FEM) and random effects model (REM). The implementation of different methods is to ensure that the assumption in the methods is not violated, helping to produce reliable regression results. Besides, the Wooldridge test and Breusch-Pagan test with significance level of 5% are performed to check the defects of model such as test series autocorrelation or variable variance.

Data used for analyzing is mainly collected from World Bank database and the BP statistical review of BP in period 2000 – 2020, and then processed by Stata software version 16. The descriptive statistics for some issues in Vietnam are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive results

Variable	Unit	Mean	Min	Max	Std. Dev
Economic Growth	%	6.24	2.6	7.5	1.29
Exchange rate	LCU per US\$	18,945.86	14,167.75	23,208.37	3,253.14
Energy transition	%	0.49	0	6.24	1.42
CO ₂ Emissions	Million ton	160.3	51.21	336.49	83.27
Population growth	%	0.98	0.8	1.1	0.08

Source: Results from Stata

Table 1 shows that the average annual economic growth of Vietnam is 6.24% over 2000 – 2021, the maximum is 7.5% (in 2004 and 2005). The energy transition just started in 2005 but the rate of change is very slow. Over this period, the average of energy transition is 0.09%, the highest is in 2021 with 0.27%. During this time, CO₂ Emissions in Vietnam is about 160.3 million tons in average, the maximum of CO₂ even reaches 336.49 million ton in some months.

After getting the descriptive results, researchers continue to conduct Pearson correlations analysis. The purpose of these steps is to check whether the dependent variable and independent variables have significant relationship. Table 2 below provides the results of this analysis in detail.

Table 2. Pearson correlation results

	Econom- ics Growth	Exchange rate	CO ₂ Emis- sions	Popula- tion growth	Energy transition
Econom- ics Growth	1.0000				
Exchange rate	-0.3768 0.0839	1.0000			
CO ₂ Emissions	-0.3273 0.1371	0.9424 0.0000	1.0000		
Popula- tion growth	0.2897 0.1910	0.0436 0.8474	-0.0549 0.8083	1.0000	
Energy transition	-0.7749 0.0000	0.4535 0.0340	0.5138 0.0144	-0.5643 0.0062	1.0000

Source: Stata's results

Table 2 shows that all sig. value of independent variables and energy transition is smaller than 0.05, it can be temporally concluded that economic growth, exchange rate, CO₂ emissions and population growth have relationship with energy transition. Four hypotheses mentioned in this research are accepted.

Table 3. Regression results

	Coef	Std. Err	T	p > t	Beta
Economics Growth	-0.67	0.13	-5.06	0.000	-0.60
Exchange rate	-0.00	0.00	-1.05	0.307	-0.35

CO ₂ emissions	0.01	0.01	1.94	0.069	0.63
Population growth	-6.42	2.18	-2.95	0.009	-0.34
_cons	12.13	2.42	5.02	0.000	

Source: Stata analysis results

Following Table 3 of regression results, p-value of exchange rate and CO₂ emissions are higher than 0.05, two independent variables have no relationship with energy transition in Vietnam. Furthermore, with p-value of 0.0005 and coef. Value of -0.67, economics growth shows the negative influence to energy transition in Vietnam. It also can be understood that when economics growth increases 1 unit, energy transition is reduced 0.67 unit and vice versa. Similarly, population growth has p-value of 0.009 < 0.05 and coef. Value of -6.42, it means if there are any adjustments and the population growth is changed of one unit, energy transition will be impacted on the opposite way and change 6.42 units.

To check whether the model has serial correlation or not, the Wooldridge test is conducted with the following pair of hypotheses:

- H0: No serial correlation phenomenon
- H1: There is a serial correlation phenomenon

To check whether the model has the phenomenon of heteroscedasticity, the author uses the Breusch-Pagan test with the following pair of hypotheses:

- H0: There is no heteroscedasticity
- H1: There is a phenomenon of heteroscedasticity in the model.

The results of Wooldridge test and Breusch-Pagan test (p-value > 0.05) show that there are no defects of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity in the model.

The regression equation of energy transition in Vietnam has the following form:

Energy transition = 12.13 – 0.67 economics growth – 6.42 population growth

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This research contributes to the energy transition discourse by focusing on the unique financial and regulatory challenges faced by a state-owned utility like EVN, which is critical to the success of Vietnam's energy transition but is also constrained by structural limitations. Unlike existing research, which often fo-

cuses on the technical aspects of energy storage, this study provides a more holistic approach by addressing the intersection of financial, regulatory, and technological barriers. Additionally, by considering a wide array of energy storage technologies—including PSH, lithium-ion batteries, and hydrogen storage—this research offers a broader perspective on how Vietnam can meet its COP26 commitments despite EVN’s financial struggles. The findings and recommendations are practical, providing actionable insights into how EVN can navigate its financial difficulties while still pursuing large-scale energy transition goals.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

Limitations: The study is focused on EVN and does not fully explore the role of private energy enterprises or the potential impact of international market conditions on Vietnam’s energy transition.

Practical implications: The research provides concrete recommendations for EVN, including alternative financing strategies and the selection of cost-effective energy storage technologies that can be implemented in the near term. These findings can also inform national energy policies, particularly regarding regulatory reforms and investment incentives.

Social implications: Successfully implementing the proposed energy storage solutions will ensure a stable energy supply, support Vietnam’s sustainable development goals, and reduce the social and environmental impacts of climate change, improving quality of life for citizens.

CONCLUSION

The global situation of energy transition is at a pivotal juncture, marked by a growing recognition of the urgent need to shift towards sustainable energy systems. Research on energy transition is essential due to the critical role it plays in addressing climate change, enhancing energy security, and promoting sustainable development worldwide. The urgency of transitioning to sustainable energy systems necessitates a thorough understanding of the drivers, barriers, and pathways involved. By conducting research on energy transition, policymakers, businesses, and civil society can make informed decisions, develop effective strategies, and implement targeted interventions to accelerate the transition. Moreover, research helps identify innovative solutions, technological advancements, and best practices that can facilitate the transition process. Ultimately, investing in research on energy transition is imperative for shaping a sustainable and resilient future for generations to come. Ultimately, this research provides a roadmap for EVN to navigate its financial and operational challenges, helping Vietnam meet its COP26 commitments while ensuring a stable, sustainable energy future.

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